

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH**Yusupova S.T.****TITLI**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19508721>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 06TH April 2026Accepted: 08th April 2026Online: 10th April 2026**KEYWORDS**

English language, modern methods, communicative approach, speech activity, language teaching, methodology, learning process, interactive methods

ABSTRACT

This article discusses modern methods of teaching English, their theoretical foundations, and practical significance. The role of language in human life is substantiated, and various approaches to foreign language teaching are analyzed. Special attention is given to the communicative method, its essence, principles, and role in the educational process. Furthermore, the ways of developing students' communicative competence through modern teaching materials are highlighted. The findings indicate that the integrated use of different methods increases the effectiveness of language teaching.

The development of science shows that the role of language in human life is extremely significant. Language is not only a means of communication, but it also greatly influences a person's individual characteristics, emotional experiences, psychological state, culture, health, and even professional activity. Therefore, it is not without reason that our people say: "Language is the key to the heart," "A doctor should first treat a patient with words," and "Language is the measure of intellect."

Language is a complex and multifaceted historical phenomenon that holds intellectual, spiritual, and cultural significance for every individual and every professional. That is why the "National Program for Personnel Training" emphasizes that improving language education and implementing it on the basis of effective modern methods is one of the most urgent state-level tasks in our republic.

In the methodology of teaching English, the term "method" has three meanings:

1. A whole direction in the history of methodology (grammar-translation method, comparative method, direct method, oral method, mixed method, etc.);
2. A teaching system within a particular methodological direction (for example, the methods of François Gouin, Harold Palmer, M. West, Ch. Fries, R. Lado);
3. A way of interaction between teacher and learner (presentation, practice, and application methods).

The methodology of teaching English has a long history, during which linguists and methodologists have developed numerous approaches to language teaching. Today, 16 methods with scientific and practical foundations are recognized in foreign language teaching methodology. These methods are named either according to educational goals (grammar-translation, text-translation, oral method, direct method, conscious-comparative, intensive,

communicative methods) or after the scholars who developed them (G. Lozanov, Ch. Fries, R. Lado, H. Palmer, M. West, François Gouin, G.A. Kitaygorodskaya).

The emergence of particular methods is associated with social, political, scientific, economic, and cultural factors. For instance, in the mid-19th century, due to the expansion of international relations, the grammar-translation and text-translation methods no longer met the demands of the time. As a result of advances in science (psychology, linguistics, and technology), audio-visual and audio-lingual methods were developed.

Analysis of methodological literature and teaching experience shows that each method has both advantages and disadvantages. Among modern methods, the communicative method is one of the most widely recognized.

One of the main features of the communicative method is teaching students to communicate through all types of speech activity: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. To understand its essence, it is necessary to consider the principles underlying this method:

1. Functionality of language material (its relevance for communication),
2. Acceleration of students' speech production,
3. Consideration of situational context in teaching,
4. Consideration of learners' individual characteristics,
5. Inclusion of new and meaningful information in teaching materials,
6. Use of the studied material in all types of speech activity.

To better understand and effectively apply the communicative method, it is recommended to refer to recently published textbooks such as Word Wise, Happy English, Day by Day, Headway, World English, and others.

Most exercises presented in these textbooks are communicative in nature and are based on learners' life experiences, encouraging them to communicate in English and to understand spoken and written materials.

From the perspective of educational objectives, the exercises in these materials can be divided into three groups:

1. Exercises developing language skills,
2. Exercises developing communicative competence,
3. Exercises developing students' worldview and thinking abilities.

The essence of the communicative method lies in organizing the learning process as real communication, that is, structuring the lesson in the same way as natural speech interaction occurs.

This method can be used both for teaching language material and for developing speech skills. Another important feature is that it requires the use of pre-communicative and communicative exercises.

Common techniques used in the communicative approach include:

1. Induced information gap (providing intentionally incomplete or differing information),
2. Option gap (presenting logically inconsistent information),
3. Information exchange,
4. Problem solving,
5. Role play,
6. Language games,

7. Group discussion.

Based on teaching experience and observations, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Teachers should understand the essence, principles, and application of each method;
2. It is advisable to identify the strengths of different methods and apply them appropriately in the teaching process;

3. Teaching should not be limited to textbooks only; it is important to use additional materials such as supplementary books, newspapers, journals, radio, and television programs.

In addition, to improve language education, it is recommended to:

1. Regularly study methodological literature (such as journals like “Language and Literature Teaching,” “Russian Language Abroad,” “Foreign Languages at School,” “Teaching Language and Literature”), as well as recent monographs and textbooks;

2. Attend each other’s lessons and improve open classes;

3. Study international teaching experience..

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